

Studies on Hydroxo Cyanogen Compounds: III. A Spectrophotometric Study of the Reaction of U (VI) with Potassium Aquo-Trihydroxotetracyanomolybdate (IV)

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Tripotassium aquo-trihydroxotetracyanomolybdate (IV) in aqueous solution forms a reddish-brown water soluble complex with uranium (VI). The molar composition as determined by Job's as well as molar ratio methods has been found to be 1 : 1. The average value of $\log K = 3.71 \pm 0.24$ and $\Delta F^\circ = -5.08$ Kcals/mole at 25°.

In an earlier communication from this laboratory the formation of a soluble complex between potassium aquo-trihydroxotetracyanomolybdate (IV) and vanadium (IV)¹ has been described. No other soluble complex of the reagent is reported in the literature. The results of studies on the uranium (VI) complex of the reagent are reported here.

EXPERIMENTAL

Reagents : Potassium aquo-trihydroxotetracyanomolybdate (IV) dihydrate, $K_3[Mo(CN)_4(OH)_3(H_2O)] \cdot 2H_2O$ ^{2,3,4} was obtained by water hydrolysis of $K_4[Mo(CN)_4(OH)_4]$ prepared by the method of Jakob *et al.*⁵. Its solution was standardized potentiometrically by titrating with $K_3[Fe(CN)_6]$ ⁶.

A stock solution of uranyl acetate was prepared from the 'Baker Analysed' $UO_2(C_2H_3O_2)_2 \cdot 2H_2O$ and was standardized gravimetrically using oxine method⁷.

Absorbance measurements were made with a Bausch and Lomb spectronic 20 colorimeter.

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RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Stability of the Colour : The colour development between UO_2^{++} and the reagent is not instantaneous. Time-absorbance study shows that the development is complete in about 50 minutes. Hence all the measurements were made after 75 minutes of mixing the reactants.

Absorbance Studies : Mixtures containing varying proportions of UO_2^{++} solution : reagent were prepared and absorbance in each case was measured at suitable wave length intervals in the visible range. The absorbance values went on decreasing with increase in wave-length. At $350 \text{ m}\mu$ it was highest. Spectra of the mixtures prepared were also taken after 2, 5, 10, 24 hrs. and after keeping at 50° for 1 hr., but the behaviour was similar and absorbance decreases. The wave-length found suitable to work with was $380 \text{ m}\mu$ as the absorbances of hydroxomolybdocyanide and uranyl acetate were very low at this wave-length.

Stoichiometry of the Components : The stoichiometric ratio of UO_2^{++} to the reagent was determined by the methods of continuous variation⁸ and mole ratio⁹. A 1 : 1 composition of the complex has been confirmed by these methods. Hence the formula of the complex may be given as $\text{KUO}_2[\text{Mo}(\text{CN})_4(\text{OH})_3(\text{H}_2\text{O})]$.

Stability of the Complex : The log of formation constant has been calculated from the continuous variation curves with absorbance as the ordinate and the composition of the mixtures as abscissa. The formula used being $K = x/(a-x)(b-x)$, where the symbols have their usual meanings¹⁰. An average value of $\log K = 3.71 \pm 0.24$ at 25° was obtained. The corresponding free energy of formation (ΔF°_{298}) has been calculated as -5.08 Kcal/mole .

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